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SEEN IN A NEW LIGHT: EVALUATION OF LIGHT QUALITY FROM LED FITTINGS

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses a new method of evaluating light quality in relation to specific light fixtures. All existing studies of light quality have taken place in laboratory settings and the qualitative aspect of the participant's experience is limited. In order to address these limitations a two-stage process for evaluation of the artefacts was developed. The first stage used an already established technique from the lighting area and the second stage used technique from Computer Human Interface (CHI), a technique that was adapted to fit with this study. This evaluation process is part of a wider study that involves the design of light fittings suitable for LED sources. The paper reports on how the each stage of the evaluation process was carried out, the nature of data elicited, and the themes that emerged from the data. The paper concludes with an analysis of the value of this mixed method approach to the evaluation of light quality.

Keywords: Lighting, light quality, evaluation.

INTRODUCTION

The research question in this study is concerned with the exploration of the light from LEDs within contexts that are sensitive to the quality of light. In particular I am interested in the general lighting in domestic residential environments which need to be penetrated by LED technology for energy saving reasons.

Research around the issue of light quality began in the early 20th century, with the introduction of the fluorescent lamp - the first artificial light source that did not use some form of incandescence (whether it be burning oil, candle wax, gas or an electrical filament such as in the Edison Swan lamp).

McGowan and Miller (1998) talk of the "lighting revolution - an age of abundant light" which was sparked by the fluorescent lamp, a light source that produced a higher intensity light than had been witnessed before this time.

Incandescent sources, while they are inefficient in terms of energy consumption, produce a light spectrum that is similar to the sun (which is comfortable for our eyes). Fluorescent light, and later, LED light, which rely on other processes, do not match this spectrum. This is particularly an issue for lighting at night. Our eyes will tolerate uncomfortable light during the day but are less tolerant at night, particularly in places of "relaxation and social activity" (Hopkinson and Collins, 1970).

In their early days, fluorescent light was considered to have poor colour rendering and a very cool (unpleasantly so) colour temperature - this has been improved with research. Glare, which was the first aspect of light quality to be researched (Guth, 1961, Hopkinson and Longmore, 1959) has been an issue which has been partially addressed by better quality of manufacture of the lamps and fixture design.

Light from fluorescent light is flat and even with little shadowing. Whilst the light is considered appropriate for factories and working areas, it can be seen as dull in interior schemes.

LED's are small intense dots of light which can be hard on the eyes. The flow of light comes from one point rather than a length of tube. They are directional rather than omni-directional like existing artificial light sources such as incandescent or fluorescent. The light produced is "crisp" with shadowing of greater intensity which can detract from the look of interiors. Direct exposure to high intensity LEDs can result in feelings of discomfort glare from the viewer (Kasahara et al., 2006).

On the other hand, the light from the incandescent lamp is considered warm and inviting. Its connection with domesticity summed up by the expression “Incandescent coziness” (Kellog, 2009).

Developments in new light sources attempt to emulate the light from the incandescent lamp - particularly for the domestic residential environment.

THE QUESTION OF LIGHT QUALITY - TOWARDS A DEFINITION

An understanding of light quality in LED fittings begins with a definition of light quality factors. However, there is a degree of contention with these definitions. Some researchers bring an engineering approach with quantifiable measurements of glare etc. Others have a human factors approach which includes worker comfort and productivity. So a variety of sources were consulted to identify the following factors for the purposes of this study.

The light from artefact is acceptable and provides comfort and satisfaction with no glare.

Glare, defined as brightness which can “produce a feeling of discomfort” (IES, 2009), has been identified as an issue in the use of LEDs (Reo, 2008). Whilst absence of glare is important, too much emphasis on the removal of glare can result in flat and mediocre lighting schemes (Marsden, 1972). Other issues need to be considered as well as glare prevention.

The light from artefact creates the mood appropriate to the setting such as a hallway, living room wall or other environment in which the light fitting is placed.

Domestic residences place great demands on light and there is an expectation that the light will actively contribute to the atmosphere of the dwelling. Marsden (1972) describes this as a type of revelation where the lighting reveals the environment to its best advantage. He notes this as an artistic and subjective aspect. However, it is not enough for the space to look attractive - it is important that it also “influences social interaction, fosters mood and atmosphere” (IES, 2009) and that the mood, atmosphere and degree of social interaction are right for the context.

The light contributes to task performance and the level of light is correct for the task.

Each context within a household will have different tasks - some of which could be as simple as hanging a coat or as complex as cooking a meal. The right amount of visibility is required for the particular task at hand and it is important that the light allows “people to gain just the right amount of information” (Tregenza and Loe, 1998). Too little and the task is difficult, too much and the viewer feels fatigued and overwhelmed.

The light and light fitting complements the physical space in terms of the light created, appearance of the fitting and its integration into the environment.

This is a more complex requirement. People select lighting on the basis that it meet all the requirements above but also that it complements their interior spaces. Marsden (1972) defines this as the requirement for lighting to communicate what is important about the actual architectural space. This is dependent on the visual appearance of the lighting units and their placement. This notion that the light fitting and the light itself “beautifies the space and architecture” (IES, 2009) or at least complements and enhances the space is important in the domestic sphere.

It is important to note that light quality cannot be reduced to a series of quantifiable measurements (such as colour temperature) so attention must be paid to qualitative aspects of the overall experience of the light in contexts.

LIMITATIONS OF EXISTING APPROACHES TO THE EVALUATION OF LIGHT QUALITY

Early research into light quality took an engineering approach (Guth 1961) with an emphasis on measurement. In the 1970's, a more qualitative approach was taken by John Flynn and his colleagues around the psychology of light (Flynn et al., 1979). The latest developments are around how lighting quality effects social behaviour, health, mood, task performance and aesthetic judgments and are a development of the work of Flynn. There is an emphasis on comfort and productivity of working people. This is exemplified by the work of Jennifer

Veitch and Guy Newsham (Veitch and Newsham, 1996).

Most existing and current research into light quality is situated within a laboratory. The study might be based around investigation of glare where a variety of lighting sources were shown to the subjects and the subjects recorded a response (Kasahara et al., 2006). Other studies have looked at preferences and behaviours of subject when exposed to different lighting levels and lighting directions (Chiu and Chen, 2010, Hopkinson and Longmore, 1959, Taylor et al., 1974).

It is rare to find a field study around lighting - the few that have been undertaken take place in specially designed office environments (Newsham et al., 2010). This type of work attracts funding so the research tends to stay in the office/commercial area where the light quality requirements are different to those of the domestic residential areas which are being examined in this study.

Whilst homes have areas for tasks (the kitchen, for example) they also need to be places of relaxation and social activity. People have an emotional attachment to their homes and this study needed responses that evoked *how* the subject felt when the light was in their homes. The variety of materials, textures and shapes within a home, which are not present in laboratories or offices, create specific challenges for lighting. There do not appear to be any detailed field studies evaluating light quality in residential or other related environments. Context or lack of it is an issue with current lighting research. There is also a question on the type of responses obtained from these studies. With existing techniques there is little opportunity for open ended responses which could enrich the data. Any qualitative material is limited to a pre-determined set of criteria.

A NEW TECHNIQUE FOR EVALUATING LIGHT QUALITY WITHIN A RESIDENTIAL CONTEXT.

This section discusses the development of a two stage technique for evaluation light quality in a residential context which addresses some of the limitations of previous studies.

“DOMESTICATION” TECHNIQUE.

An evaluation process needed to be used which could take into consideration context as well as providing the evocative qualitative responses necessary for understanding how these artefacts could work within the domestic residential environment.

Routarinne & Redstrom (2007) working within the domain of Computer Human Interface design, developed a technique of evaluation around the “domestication” of two experimental prototypes”. Their study involved leaving the experimental prototypes in a household for a period of time and seeing how the household reacted to and used the objects. Subjects were interviewed at the end of the process on how they used the artefact. Routarinne & Redstrom were guided by three questions:

- How will the users receive the prototype?
- Do they interpret them in accordance with the design intentions embedded in them?
- Will the prototypes find a slot in the material and social system of the house?

One of the aims of domestication is to address the issue of the introduction of a new technology into an existing system. The domestication approach will generate feedback on how this newer technology (LEDs) would be received and used within a household which has an existing system of lighting involving other sources.

The domestication approach offers a richer canvas of data than a laboratory based experiment. This study is being undertaken from a design perspective and involves understanding how this new technology can address the “needs and desires” (Hutchinson et al., 2003) of users. However, there are other types of information which can be obtained from the domestication approach. According to Hutchinson et al there is the social science goal of understanding the use of the technology within a real world setting and a more engineering goal of testing the effectiveness of the technology itself.

This experience of domestication was also part of my own professional practice as a lighting designer. When developing new lighting products I would set up a prototype version in a corner of a room in constant use and live with it for a period of time. I found the dynamic relationship with the lighting

prototype (seen at various times of the day, looking at it with “fresh eyes” when I re-entered the room, understanding how it might work within an interior context) to be very helpful.

SEMANTIC DIFFERENTIAL SCALING

Though the “domestication” approach provided the opportunity to understand how the artefact would work within a household, there was still a still the need to obtain subjective responses around the quality of light. Lighting is frequently accepted in without too much critical examination and could be described as existing “below the level of consciousness” (Canter, 1974).

An approach to obtaining subjective responses that has appeared in the literature is known as *semantic differential scaling* which was developed by John Flynn (Flynn et al., 1973) and has become widely used in obtaining qualitative responses to light. Tiller and Rea (1992) describe semantic differential scaling as a seven category rating scales which are defined by polar opposites. The subject in the study then chooses a point along a 7 point continuum between the opposites which best matches his experience of the light. Examples of differential scaling from Flynn would be Friendly/ Hostile, Pleasant/ Unpleasant, Glare/ Non-glare. However, despite its usefulness, semantic differential scaling it has limitations in providing the open ended qualitative feedback I was looking for in the study.

For this study a version of the Flynn model was used in conjunction with the domestication process. The scaling acted as an initial “probe” prompting the use of the type of language needed to make the data obtained at the exit point useful. The aim was to sensitise the subject to a variety of dimensions of light quality and enhance their awareness of particular light sources.

There is also the added benefit that the use of this method would establish a connection from my study to the existing lighting research.

Flynn suggests that rating scales should be selected as appropriate to the context and goals of the experiment (Flynn et al., 1979). He also suggested that, whilst there is no theoretical limit on the number of scales used, subject fatigue could be a limiting factor. The scales have discrete steps rather than continuous scales (such as Visual Analogue

Scale) in line with lighting industry practice and to maintain some level of consistency between respondents..

Diffuse								Glarey
Relaxed								Tense
Soft								Hard
Welcoming								Unwelcoming
Restful								Lively
Harmonious								Discordant
Informal								Formal
Intimate								Aloof

Table 1. Subjects were asked to rate the light from this artefact as to whether it provides comfort and satisfaction with no glare.

Adequate								Inadequate
Clear								Hazy

Table 2. Subjects were asked to rate the light from this artefact for tasks.

Informal								Formal
Private								Public
Pleasant								Unpleasant
Welcoming								Unwelcoming
Spacious								Cramped

Table 3. Subjects were asked to rate their experience of the space when the light was on. This scale rated the mood created by the light.

Table 3 scale also tried to get feedback on what type of residential light the artefact could be i.e. public situations (hallway) or more private locations (bedroom).

Informal								Formal
Private								Public
Harmonious								Discordant
Welcoming								Unwelcoming
Focus of attention								Blends in with background

Table 4. Subjects were asked to rate the appearance of the artefact in this space.

OPEN ENDED QUESTIONS

Whilst the semantic differential scaling would assist in developing the language, the questions at the exit interview stage after the domestication process would provide the necessary data for the study. The four light quality factors, identified above, were used as a basis for the open ended questions. It was

important that the subject's responses to the performance of the artefact in relation to these criteria was understood. This information would enable the researcher to evaluate *how* the artefacts performed as light fittings in a general illumination environment

The first four questions (listed below) addressed light quality factors in terms of comfort, mood / atmosphere, task performance and the function of the artefact and light within the space. There was also an opportunity to comment specifically on the appearance of the artefact. This aspect is important in the wider research question (of which this study is a part) which is exploring possible typologies of form and material choice that could be appropriate for use with LEDs.

1. What was the experience of the space/ room with this light in terms of the mood and atmosphere?
2. How did the lighting affect any tasks that you may need to complete in the area?
3. Could you live with this lighting artefact in that space long term?
4. Overall do you think this artefact suitable for your dwelling in terms of:
 - Light quality
 - Appearance of the artefact itself
 - Function of the artefact (i.e. the fact it is a wall fitting, the spread of light etc).

These were important issues in the study and I wanted to discuss them at the beginning while the subject was not under time pressures and the energy level was high. It also gave the subject an opportunity to revisit them later if new ideas came up in discussion.

After these questions, the subject was then asked to comment upon other contexts for the artefact and given an opportunity to make suggestions as to possible design directions. This information would also shed some light on how the artefact would be integrated household. The final questions were about the subject's attitude to lighting to see if there were any experiences or opinions that had influenced their feedback.

5. Are there other contexts in your home where it would be suitable - any that are unsuitable?

6. Are there any non- residential contexts it could be used in e.g. hotel, restaurant, and office?
7. Any other comments on the artefact, light or this process.
8. How would you define your overall attitude to lighting generally?

I framed the questions with the aim of eliciting subjective responses and with a view to encouraging the use of evocative language to describe the experience of the light in the space.

THE STUDY

ARTEFACTS

Research into light mediation through luminaires (light fittings) revealed that there are a number of optical principles which can be used - reflection, diffusion and refraction (McDermott et al., 2010). The two artefacts that were used in this part of the study were essentially the same design. By changing the materials, one artefact used the principle of diffusion the other used the principle of reflection. The artefact itself was a type of louvre used the wall surface as part of the lighting effect. The 'gull-wing profile' was developed to reflect light out the side most effectively.

Each artefact was mounted over an array of LEDs which were a strip of Nichia Flexi-ribbon 120 12Volts DC with colour temperature of 3200 K. This colour is considered a neutral colour temperature. The artefact and LED array were mounted on a board approximately 600mm square with a power cord. The LED drivers were mounted internally for safety and ease of transportation.

The diffusion artefact was made from clear acrylic painted white on the upper side. The effect of the light source was diffuse and softer. The reflection artifact used stainless steel - polished on the underside with a brushed finish on the outer surface. The aim was for a more hard edged 'architectural' appearance of both the artefact itself and the lighting effect.

Figure 1. Lighting artefact based on the principle of diffusion.

Figure 2. Lighting artefact based on the principle of reflection.

METHOD

The diffusion artefact (as with the reflection artefact) was delivered and set up in a living / dining area, hallway or vestibule. The choice of placement in the home was driven by the need for visibility so a public space such as a hallway or living area was chosen. Subjects were told to move the artefact to another area if they wished. However, in most households it was difficult to do this as the artefact was mounted on a large board and needed support and plenty of room. However, Household 4 did place the artefact in three different areas (see below).Subjects also had the opportunity to specify where the artefact would be best situated which was important information for the study.

The artefact was left there for a minimum of 48 hours - though the time was frequently longer. However, the time was kept to a few days to ensure that the subject still had a reasonably accurate memory of the space before the intervention of the artefact.

The subject also received a semantic differential scaling with a suggestion to fill out near the exit point so information would be fresh however the timing was left up to the subject. When the artefact was collected an exit interview took place.

SUBJECTS

The subjects for this two-stage approach were residential light users who were selected from personal and professional networks. The selection of particular subjects was based on two criteria.

A spread of ages was important as research has found that the human eye becomes more sensitive to glare as the person ages (Hopkinson and Collins, 1970) and glare had been identified as an issue around LED lighting (Reo, 2008). So subjects ranged in ages from early twenties to sixty.

Subjects and their households were imagined in terms of archetypes. So there were the relatively uncluttered and controlled environments of younger single and coupled people with no children to the busier households with children.

	Household	Subjects and ages
1	2 adults no children	2 x males both in 20's
2	2 adults no children	1 x female, 1 x male 30's
3	2 adults, 3 schoolchildren	1 x female 40's
4	2 adults, 2 university aged children	3 x male 60's, 20's, 18yrs 1 x female 50's

Table 5. Households/ subjects for study.

Household 1 had younger people who were working long hours - the household could be described as modern, minimalist and uncluttered. Household 2 the people in their 30's were spending more time at home - there were more decorative aspects than Household 1. Household 3 was a busy household with school age children involved in a variety of activities such as sport, music etc. The house itself was older and full of interesting ornaments and heritage items. Household 4 had older children who were more engaged outside the house. The house itself was less cluttered than Household 3 though had a variety of artworks and books.

Care was taken *not* to select people who had a professional involvement in lighting design. The feedback needed to reflect the common experience of lighting in the residential sector i.e. no

professional experience in the area. The number of subjects needed to be balanced between providing enough variety in data and the practical aspects of running a study such as this in terms of time and resources. Formosa (2009) suggests that qualitative research of this kind can be effective by using around six people who represent diversity and complexity within the area to be explored. Whilst the number could be higher, he also argues that it is hard to even please six people and that a group this size will have real and contrasting views.

Figure 3. Diffusion artefact in Household 1.

Figure 4. Reflection artefact in Household 2.

Figure 5. Reflection artefact in Household 3.

Figure 6. Reflection artefact in Household 4 in vestibule area.

Figure 7. Diffusion artefact in Household 4 in television room

Figure 8. Diffusion artefact in television room of Household 4. The artefact was placed above couch opposite television. This placement was requested by family.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS OF DOMESTICATION FOR THE DIFFUSION ARTEFACT.

The following discussion is based around the three questions addressed by domestication as outlined above and incorporates the subject's reaction to the light quality.

HOW DID THE USERS RECEIVE THE PROTOTYPE?

The light quality was seen as pleasant and acceptable. Words such as "lightweight, soft, halo effect" were used. The light was seen to have some warmth and create a relaxed, calm ambience to the area it was placed in. There was no evidence of discomfort glare.

However, with some subjects there was still a sense of distance exemplified by the phrase describing the light as "Pleasant but not drawn to it." Some subjects thought the light was warm enough others would have liked something slightly warmer. Subjects were divided on the appearance of the artefact itself. Some liked the artefact's appearance stating that the folded louvre shape integrated into the wall. Others thought it was too "architectural" possibly clinical with the sharp folds and lacked the "homey" look suitable for domestic use. It was generally agreed that the style of the interior needed to match the artefact and there would be some interiors that would suit it better than others. There was some feedback around different sizes, materials and formats (suggestion of a horizontal orientation) for artefact.

There was generally positive feedback on how the light functioned within the space in terms of atmosphere created. The way the light radiated out from the artefact and washed across the wall was seen as a positive. One subject even went so far as to comment on the light coming from the side as being "more romantic - something to do with sunsets".

As far as tasks, the light was adequate for passing through the space. Reading was possible if you were reasonably close by. It was also adequate for hanging coats, getting dog lead (when placed in a vestibule). This artefact was successfully used as a television room light - giving enough light to watch television comfortably and read the television guide if the placement was correct.

DO THEY INTERPRET THEM IN ACCORDANCE WITH THE DESIGN INTENTIONS EMBEDDED IN THEM?

The artefact was designed to create a light fitting using LED technology which be used in a domestic residential situation. All subjects could live with the light with their homes - some within the current context but many wanted to place it within another context (see next section).

WILL THE PROTOTYPE FIND A SLOT IN THE MATERIAL AND SOCIAL SYSTEM OF THE HOUSE?

The subjects were generally positive about having the diffusion artefact as a real light fitting within their homes. However, they wanted control as to where and how it was placed.

One subject described the diffusion artefact as "a good hall light" and this was supported by other suggestions of hallways, vestibules, stairwells as contexts. Some subjects identified the light and artefact as having a more formal, public type of appearance which suited these placements. The idea of having a very long version on a stairwell wall which would connect the different floors was suggested.

In one household the diffusion artefact had a journey through three different placements. The first was in a vestibule, the second (propped up on a table) and third (hung on the wall behind a couch) placements were in the upstairs television room. This was requested by the subjects and seen as a successful placement by the entire household (and visitors). Four subjects suggested bathrooms as a possible placement. This was an unexpected result as bathrooms are demanding areas for light quality however, there is a task aspect to bathrooms and the crisp light from the artefact may be appropriate for this area. Also the appearance of the artefact with the crisp folds would suit this area.

There were also some temporal issues as well. One subject (a shiftworker) liked the light quality in the early morning when it was dark. He felt the fitting did not bombard him with too much light and it was a good transition from dark to full light.

This idea of the artefact performing a transitional role was supported by a placement in a vestibule where another subject liked the linkage between the exterior porch light and the well lit living room.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS OF DOMESTICATION FOR THE REFLECTION ARTEFACT.

HOW DID THE USERS RECEIVE THE PROTOTYPE?

As one subject noted, you either loved or hated this artefact. Whilst there were some positive words (festive, fancy, dramatic, complex, interesting) to describe the light, it was seen to be more localised, less comfortable and less functional than the light from the diffusion artefact.

The artefact itself also divided the responses. Some liked the sculptural aspects of the folded sheet metal; others thought it was not appropriate for a domestic interior. Other materials such as ceramic were suggested as well as other design alterations such as perforations in the metal or curving the "gull wings" of the louvre. Many referred to this artefact as more of an artwork (dramatic statement, feature light, attention demanding).

As the light itself was more localized, the effect on the surrounds was less than the diffusion light. However, the long strip of light up the wall was remarked upon as a positive by many subjects. One subject placed the reflection artefact in the hall and found that visitors asked about this artefact much more than the diffusion artefact. They were curious about the light source and many liked the patterns the artefact created.

DO THEY INTERPRET THEM IN ACCORDANCE WITH THE DESIGN INTENTIONS EMBEDDED IN THEM?

This artefact was designed (as with the diffusion artefact) to use LEDs to create a light fitting suitable for a domestic residential situation. Many subjects liked the artefact but did not think that it would be appropriate for a domestic interior situation. They felt there would be many commercial, hospitality situations that it would suit.

There was also a sense that any interior would need to be designed to suit this artefact - the artefact was too modern and severe for the average domestic interior. The reflection artefact would be a specified product from an architect.

WILL THE PROTOTYPES FIND A SLOT IN THE MATERIAL AND SOCIAL SYSTEM OF THE HOUSE?

Exterior lighting was suggested as a possible context. The other contexts would be quite specific e.g. as a

dramatic feature light at the end of a hall to draw the eye, functioning like an artwork. One subject would have it as a night light in a vestibule.

The general sense was that, though the artefact in some ways was more interesting than the diffusion, it would be difficult to place find a place for it in their homes.

CONCLUSIONS

The two part process was able to create data which gave me a better understanding of many aspects of the performance (design, social science, and engineering) of these artefacts within a domestic residence. The light quality factors were covered with a type of evocative language which related to the domestic environment. There was also some interesting design directions suggested in terms of size and materials for the artefact. The suggestions from the subjects as to how they would use the artefact within the existing household system also gave a sense of how effective the current design was and how it could be improved.

The semantic differential scaling was created to assist with the quality of the feedback. One subject was asked whether the scaling assisted with the feedback and her response was:

I have to say yes, that the scaling definitely helped me to think about the different qualities / characteristics of light when evaluating it and describing the experience to you. It definitely allowed me to focus more on these different aspects of lighting and consider the experience from a much broader / richer perspective (rather than the continuum between "I like it" - "I don't like it").

The domestication aspect gave a better sense of living with the light in a dynamic sense - entering the room, walking around the fitting, different times of the day. Subjects were familiar with the feeling of the space with other light sources so the intervention with the LED created a sense of difference.

The artefacts themselves were more than just light fittings. They were acting as probes to provoke responses and allow the user to "reflect upon their values, experiences and attitudes in a way not easily accessed by other means" (Routarinne and Redström, 2007).

This two part process also collected data for a specific (residential) that has *not* been covered in

other studies. It has assisted in understanding what people actually want from their lighting in their homes which will help designers to design fittings to allow LED technology greater penetration into the residential market.

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The author would like to acknowledge the assistance of Dr Sally McLaughlin and Mr Jim Franklin from the University of Technology, Sydney.